

NewsLetter

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Project Partners

September 2018

Krakow Consortium Meeting a Productive Success

The partners gathered last week in Krakow, Poland for a three-day meeting hosted by APTIV. The focus was on finishing up cycle 1, the naturalistic phase, and preparing for cycles 2 and 3, the controlled and simulated phases. Below the partners break for lunch of pizza, a variety of salads, and (of course) desserts. Thank you APTIV for your impeccable hosting!

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BrainSigns publishes 2 papers

SIMUSAFE partner, BrainSigns, publishes 2 papers

We are pleased to present two papers from BrainSigns that were recently accepted for publication. Both used research undertaken for the SIMUSAFE project.

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Physiological Measurement

TOPICAL REVIEW

Passive BCI beyond the lab: current trends and future directions

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Abstract
Over the last decade, passive brain-computer interface (BCI) algorithms and biosignal acquisition technologies have experienced a significant growth that has allowed the real-time analysis of biosignals, with the aim to quantify relevant insights, such as mental and emotional states, of the users. Several passive BCI-based applications have been tested in laboratory settings, and just a few of them in real or, at least, simulated but highly realistic settings. Nevertheless, works performed in laboratory settings are not able to take into account all those factors (artefacts, non-brain influences, other mental states) that could impair the usability of passive BCIs during real applications, naturally characterized by higher complexity.

The present review takes into account the most recent trends in using advanced passive BCI technologies in real settings, especially for real-time mental state evaluations in operational environments, evaluation of team resources, training and expertise assessment, gaming and neuromarketing applications.

The objective of the work is to draw a mark on where we are to date and the future challenges, in order to make passive BCIs closer to being integrated into daily life applications.

1. Introduction

The first attempt to evaluate the feasibility and practicality of employing brain signals in a man-computer dialogue was introduced in 1973 (Vidal 1973). In such a perspective, the machine was considered as a prosthetic extension of the user's brain. In its classical definition, the brain-computer interface (BCI) was considered as 'a communication system in which messages or commands do not pass through the brain normal output pathways of peripheral nerves and muscles' (Wolpaw *et al.* 2003).

The original aim of BCI applications was to provide a communication and/or control channel for people with severe motor disabilities (i.e. locked-in people). In fact, because of (i) the low transfer rate (25 bits min⁻¹, Wolpaw *et al.* 2002, Aricò *et al.* 2014), and depending on the brain feature of the specific user, and also (ii) the long training period (i.e. sensory motor-based BCIs), such types of systems remain a possible effective solution just for patients. Most recently, it was considered possible to explore other applications of BCI rather than only enhanced communication and additional control channels. In particular, Wolpaw and Wolpaw (2012) defined a brain-computer interface as 'a system that measures central nervous system (CNS) activity and converts it into artificial output that replaces, restores, enhances, supplements, or improves natural CNS output and thereby changes the ongoing interactions between the CNS and its external or internal environment'. From the measure of the CNS activity to the conversion into artificial output, there are few common processing steps for any kind of BCI system. In particular, a BCI records brain signals (e.g. electroencephalography (EEG), functional near infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS), etc.), extracts specific features from such signals (e.g. event-related potentials (ERPs), frequency bands), and converts (i.e. translates) these features into artificial outputs (figure 1).

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Human-Machine Interaction Assessment by Neurophysiological Measures: a Study on Professional Air Traffic Controllers

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Abstract—This study aims at investigating the possibility to employ neurophysiological measures to assess the human-machine interaction effectiveness. Such a measure can be used to compare new technologies or solutions, with the purpose to enhance operator's experience and increase safety. In the present work, two different interaction modalities (Normal and Augmented) related to Air Traffic Management field have been compared, by involving 10 professional air traffic controllers in a control tower simulated environment. Experimental task consisted in locating aircrafts in different airspace positions by using the sense of hearing. In one modality (i.e. "Normal"), all the sound sources (aircrafts) had the same amplification factor. In the "Augmented" modality, the amplification factor of the sound sources located along the participant's head sagittal axis was increased, while the intensity of sound sources located outside this axis decreased. In other words, when the user oriented his head toward the aircraft position, the related sound was amplified. Performance data, subjective questionnaires (i.e. NASA-TLX) and neurophysiological measures (i.e. EEG-based) related to the experienced workload have been collected. Results showed higher significant performance achieved by the users during the "Augmented" modality with respect to the "Normal" one, supported by a significant decreasing in experienced workload, evaluated by using EEG-based index. In addition, Performance and EEG-based workload index showed a significant negative correlation. On the contrary, subjective workload analysis did not show any significant trend. This result is a demonstration of the higher effectiveness of neurophysiological measures with respect to subjective ones for Human-Computer Interaction assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

In many operational environments (e.g. aircraft piloting, air-traffic control, industrial process control, robot-assisted surgery) operators have to face with complex systems and machines to accomplish operational activity. Improvements in such technology or even new solutions are often proposed, with the aim to enhance the human-machine interaction (HMI) and consequently increase operator's performance and consequently overall safety. In this context, the most studied user's mental state is the *Mental Workload* due to its strong relationship with the user's performance variations [1]. The mental workload can be assessed by using different approaches: i) Performance assessment e.g. by using a secondary task, provides an objective but indirect measure of the workload; ii) subjective questionnaires (e.g. NASA-TLX) provide a direct but subjective measure of the perceived workload; iii) neurophysiological measure provide both a direct and objective measure of the experienced workload [2]. With respect to the former two techniques, the latter has the advantages to not impact on the main task, since it does not require any input by the user's side, and to be available even online, i.e. during the execution of the task. A lot of works demonstrated that electroencephalography (EEG)-based workload measures outperform the other kind of techniques (e.g. EEG, fNIRS) [3]–[5]. In particular, most of the studies showed that the brain electrical activities mainly involved in the mental workload analysis are the theta and alpha brain rhythms respectively generated from the *Prefrontal Cortex* (PFC) and the *Posterior Parietal Cortex* (PPC) regions. Previous studies demonstrated that the EEG theta rhythm over the PFC presents a positive correlation with the mental workload [6]. [7]. Moreover, published literature stressed the inverse correlation between the EEG power in the alpha frequency band over the PFC and the mental workload [7]. Depending on such evidences, theta EEG rhythms over frontal sites and alpha EEG rhythms over parietal sites have been used to define an EEG-based workload index, by using the ratio between frontal theta and parietal alpha rhythms. Nowadays, there are not many studies performed in real settings demonstrating the practical advantages of neurophysiological measures for HMI assessment. For example, Borghini *et al.* [2] performed a preliminary study on few helicopter pilots in which it has been investigated a neurophysiological workload measure to compare aviation technologies. The present work targets tower ATCOs working in a small or medium size towers. In this context, sounds emitted by airplanes play a very important role to accurately locate aircrafts even without

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Passive BCI beyond the lab: current trends and future directions. Physiological measurement

Aricò, P., Reynal, M., Imbert, J. P., Hurter, C., Borghini, G., Di Flumeri, G., ... & Pozzi, S. (2018)

Human-Machine Interaction Assessment by Neurophysiological Measures: A Study on Professional Air Traffic Controllers.

Partner presentation at ASPAI' conference

Abstract

Events and interactions that take place in road junctions (i.e., roundabouts and intersections) are interesting to Naturalistic Driving Studies NDS analyzing safety and behavioral aspects of road users. This work employs machine learning techniques to develop a model that could automatically identify various road junctions encountered during ND using Inertial Measurement Unit IMU sensory data. The research is based on ND data of 16 volunteers part of SimuSafe project collected between May and August 2018.

The supervised learning approach utilizes GPS signal to label road structures. The best performing model using Random Forest classifier achieved 90% precision on roundabout identification and recorded superior recall in comparison to using smart camera to spot roundabout signs.

Partner presentation at ASPAI' conference

MDH recently presented some of their simusafe research entitled Supervised Learning for Road Junctions Identification using IMU at the International Conference on Advances in Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence (ASPAI' 2019)',

<http://www.aspai-conference.com/>

Educational Workshop

Consortium partners EFA and AIPSS held the first in a series of simusafe workshops last month in Brussels. Entitled Autonomous vehicles and road safety: towards new training modules for drivers and driving instructors.

The road mobility environment is continuously evolving and vehicle types are beginning to change as a result of increasing levels of automation: at the present vehicle SAE2 are already circulating and the SAE3 ones are close to be deployed; their interaction with conventional vehicles and other road users, particularly the vulnerable ones are an increasing concern. While the commonly accepted definition of Vulnerable Road Users includes pedestrians, cyclists, elders, impaired persons, etc., in the increasingly connected and mixed road transport system “vulnerability” may in the future be more related to the non-connected users and people unable to properly use the new technologies that will be embedded in the new generation of vehicles.

There is therefore a risk of a new “automotive digital divide” with relevant impact of socio economic and road safety aspects. In order to face the above risks and prevent the envisaged digital barrier, new education and training schemes (for both trainers and novice drivers) should be agreed at European level and implemented in a way which match the speed of the increased implementation of automated driving functions. The SIMUSAFE project is dealing with new standards related to the introduction of autonomous vehicles and organizes a series of thematic workshops. EFA and AIPSS are proud to invite you to the first one.

Festival of Innovation

Summary

Aptiv opened some of their laboratories and presented some of their ongoing projects including the SIMUSAFE project. Approximately 90 people learned about the SIMUSAFE project and Aptiv's role in developing new technology. The participants had the possibility to see eye-tracking glasses, simulated car motion data or output from driver's state camera (mounted in the simulator cockpit) on car bench (all running on a computer which is meant to be mounted in the simusafe car). Also, they could have a look into scooter instrumentation, try driving in the car and walking in the pedestrian simulators. The project met with quite favorable and enthusiastic reception.

Festival of Innovation in Krakow

Our partner, Aptiv, recently participated in Lesser Poland's Festival of Innovation in Krakow. This event was open to the general public and there was a very good audience turnout. This was also a good opportunity to educate the public about road safety, user types. Many people were so interested they volunteered right there to participate in the SIMUSAFE project!

